

1 **Analytical strategy based on asymmetric flow field flow fractionation hyphenated**
2 **to ICP-MS and complementary techniques to study gold nanoparticles**
3 **transformations in cell culture medium**

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18 **Abstract**

19 An analytical methodology based on asymmetric flow field flow fractionation
20 (AF4) hyphenated to inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS) has been
21 developed to study gold nanoparticles (AuNPs) in cell culture medium (Dulbecco's
22 Modified Eagle Medium, DMEM, containing 10 % fetal bovine serum, FBS, and
23 antibiotics) used for *in vitro* toxicological studies. AF4-ICP-MS separation of AuNPs was
24 performed using a regenerated cellulose membrane (molecular weight cut-off, MWCO,
25 of 10 kDa). The carrier composition and the AF4 separation program were optimized.
26 Under the optimum conditions, AuNPs of different types, i.e. phosphate buffered saline
27 (PBS) and citrate stabilized, and sizes (10, 30 and 40 nm), without and with cell culture
28 medium could be separated. The developed method allowed to detect transformations in
29 AuNPs and dissolved gold species (Au^{3+}) induced by this medium, such as an increase in
30 the hydrodynamic volume and oxidation. Centrifugal ultrafiltration (CU), transmission
31 electron microscopy (TEM) and Ultraviolet-visible (UV-vis) absorption
32 spectrophotometry have been used as complementary techniques to study these processes.
33 This information is of major interest to have a correct interpretation of the *in vitro*
34 toxicological studies of NPs, which are more and more demanded due to the increasing
35 concerns about the safe use of these materials and their impacts. This work demonstrates
36 the potential of hyphenated techniques based on AF4 to achieve this relevant information.

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38

39 **Keywords**

40 Gold nanoparticles; dissolved gold species; cell culture medium; asymmetric flow field
41 flow fractionation; inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry.

42

43 **1. Introduction**

44 In the last decades, the use of metallic nanoparticles (NPs) in different fields has
45 rapidly grown. Among them, gold nanoparticles (AuNPs) are widely applied in
46 electronics and sensors, solar cells or in catalysis [1–3], but they are mainly used for
47 biomedical applications, i.e. drug carriers or in cancer therapies [4–7]. Due to these
48 numerous applications, the exposure to AuNPs will increase substantially over the next
49 years and may have an impact on the environment and human health. However, little is
50 known about the fate and accumulation of AuNPs in the environment, as well as their
51 transfer to living organisms and the potential associated toxicity, and that is why
52 toxicological studies are necessary to assess the human and environmental risks of this
53 material [8].

54 Recent studies have addressed the toxicity of AuNPs in *in vivo* and *in vitro* assays,
55 the latter being the the most commonly used [9,10]. In these studies, complex biological
56 matrices, such as cell culture medium with different nutrients and antibiotics, are dealt
57 with. To obtain a correct interpretation of the toxicity results, the characterization of
58 AuNPs in these complex samples, where different transformations of the NPs can occur,
59 is very important [11–13]. Many factors, such as size, chemical composition, stabilizer
60 medium, shape, surface structure, surface charge, aggregation/agglomeration state,
61 solubility, and the presence or absence of other chemical functional groups, should be
62 taken into account and new analytical tools are necessary [14].

63 Techniques usually employed for the characterization of NPs are microscopy,
64 mainly transmission or scanning electron microscopy (TEM or SEM), and spectroscopy,
65 such as dynamic light scattering (DLS) [15]. However, all of them have limitations. TEM
66 and SEM need a sample preparation that can induce artefacts and the restricted area
67 visualized during analysis may not be representative. These techniques do not provide

68 information about the metal ionic component, either. An interesting alternative is the
69 coupling of hydrodynamic separation techniques (liquid chromatography, capillary
70 electrophoresis or field flow fractionation (FFF)) with sufficiently sensitive and selective
71 detectors (electrothermal atomic absorption (ETAAS), inductively coupled plasma
72 optical emission spectrometry (ICP-OES) or inductively coupled plasma mass
73 spectrometry (ICP-MS)). Liquid chromatography coupled to ICP-MS has been proposed
74 [12,16,17], but the separation range is rather limited [18]. Capillary electrophoresis in
75 combination with ICP-MS has also been used [19–21], but surfactant-particle interactions
76 can lead to inconsistent migration behaviours [15]. Among separation techniques, FFF,
77 particularly in the asymmetric flow mode (AF4), has emerged as one of the most
78 promising options. The main advantages of this separation technique are the resolving
79 power over a wide range of particles sizes and the minimal interaction of the analyte with
80 the surface of the operating system due to the absence of a stationary phase. FFF in
81 different modes and with different detectors (Light Scattering, UV-vis or ICP-MS) has
82 been used for polymeric [22,23] and inorganic NPs, such as quantum dots [24,25], silicon
83 dioxide [26], titanium dioxide [27,28], silver [11,29] and AuNPs [30,31]. The
84 combination of the above-mentioned favourable characteristics for NPs fractionation with
85 the highly selective and sensitive detection by ICP-MS is very advantageous [32].
86 However, as far as we know, AF4-ICP-MS has never been used for the characterization
87 of AuNPs in complex samples such as cell culture medium.

88 The aim of this work has been the development of an analytical methodology
89 based on AF4-ICP-MS to study the behaviour of AuNPs in cell culture medium used for
90 *in vitro* toxicological studies. The experimental parameters that affect AuNPs separation
91 in complex biological samples will be optimized. Some independent techniques, such as

92 centrifugal ultrafiltration (CU) and ICP-MS, TEM and UV-vis absorption
93 spectrophotometry will be used as complementary analytical tools.

94

95 **2. Materials and methods**

96

97 2.1. Materials

98 All chemicals and reagents were of analytical grade. Solutions were prepared in
99 ultrapure water, which was obtained from Milli-Q[®] A10 TM water purification system
100 (Millipore Corporation, USA). Standard AuNPs stabilized suspension in 0.1 mM
101 phosphate buffered saline (10 nm and 30 nm, AuNPs-PBS) and in 2 mM citrate (10 nm,
102 40 nm, 60 nm and 80 nm AuNPs-Citrate) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (USA)
103 and NanoComposix (USA), respectively.

104 Gold atomic absorption standard solution (1,025 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of Au^{3+} in 5 % HCl) was
105 obtained from Aldrich Chemical Company (USA). Rhodium was purchased from
106 Inorganic Ventures (USA). Sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS), methanol and sodium azide
107 were obtained from Panreac (Spain), Scharlab (Spain) and Acros Organics (Spain),
108 respectively. HCl (30 %) and HNO_3 (69 %) were purchased from Merck (Germany) and
109 Scharlab (Spain), respectively. Bovine serum albumin (BSA) was purchased from Sigma-
110 Aldrich (USA). Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium (DMEM), fetal bovine serum (FBS),
111 penicillin and streptomycin were obtained from Lonza (Spain).

112 A centrifugal filter device (Amicon[®] Ultra-0.5, 3,000 nominal molecular weight
113 limit (NMWL)) and 0.2 μm nylon filters (Agilent Technologies, Econofilter Nylon
114 diameter 13 mm) were used.

115

116 2.2. Apparatus and instrumental features

117 The AF4 system was an AF2000 (Postnova Analytics, Germany). A membrane of
118 regenerated cellulose (RC) with a molecular weight cut-off (MWCO) of 10 kDa was used
119 as the accumulation wall. The trapezoidal channel was 27.5 cm in length and from 2 to
120 0.5 cm in width, and the spacer was 350 μm thick. AF4 carrier solution was 0.01 % SDS
121 and it was filtered through 0.1 μm Teflon membrane filters (Postnova, Germany) and
122 degassed before its use. Different cross flow programs were studied to obtain a proper
123 separation of the species eluted (Supplementary material, Section S.1, Table S1), but the
124 optimal program is summarized in Table 1.

125 A Quadrupole ICP-MS Thermo X-SeriesII (Thermo Electron Corporation,
126 Germany) equipped with a Meinhard nebulizer was employed. Rhodium ($15 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) was
127 simultaneously aspirated during the ICP-MS data acquisition and it was used to correct
128 signal drifts. The raw data of the transient isotope signal for the different gold species and
129 rhodium (internal standard) were further processed using the XSeries PlasmaLab
130 software.

131 A Jeol JEM 2100 electron microscope operating at 200 kV and equipped with an
132 Energy Dispersive X-ray Spectrometer detector (Oxford Link) was used. TEM images
133 were analyzed using Digital MicrographTM software from Gatan.

134 UV-vis spectra were recorded at room temperature with a spectrophotometer
135 (Jasco Corporation, Japan) in the 190-1100 nm range using 0.1 cm path length quartz
136 cuvettes and 1.5 nm bandwidth. Data acquisition was performed using the Spectra
137 Manager software.

138 An advanced ZX3 vortex mixer (Velp Scientifica, Italy) and an ultracentrifuge
139 Digicen 21R (Orto Alresa, Spain) were used.

140

141 2.3. Preparation of AuNPs without and with cell culture medium

142 AuNPs without and with cell culture medium for the AF4-ICP-MS system were
143 prepared as reported previously with some modifications [12]. Briefly, the AuNPs
144 standards were homogenized with vortex agitation at 1200 rpm for 1 min before using. In
145 the experiments without cell culture medium, the AuNPs were diluted in 0.01 % SDS and
146 homogenized with vortex agitation during 10 s. For the experiments with cell culture
147 medium, the AuNPs were diluted in DMEM (supplemented with 10 % of FBS, 100 U
148 mL⁻¹ penicillin and 100 µg mL⁻¹ streptomycin), homogenized with vortex agitation and
149 directly injected (experiments at time = 0 h) or incubated for 24 h at 37 °C in a humidified
150 5 % CO₂ atmosphere and homogenized with vortex agitation prior to injection.

151 All standards and samples were filtered through 0.2 µm nylon filters before
152 injection into the AF4-ICP-MS system.

153 The AuNPs specimens for TEM analysis were prepared by depositing a drop of
154 the suspensions onto a holey carbon-coated copper grid and allowing it to dry for 24 h.

155

156 2.4. Centrifugal ultrafiltration

157 The centrifugal filter device was rinsed before its use with 0.5 mL of 0.1 % SDS
158 to remove the trace amounts of glycerine from the ultrafiltration membranes. All liquid
159 was removed from the device by centrifugation at 14,000 g for 10 min.

160 Then, 0.5 mL of the sample were centrifuged at 14,000 g for 20 min at 4 °C and
161 the filtrate was separated. All the ionic Au content was recovered from the membrane by
162 two additional centrifugation cycles (14,000 g for 20 min at 4 °C) with 0.15 mL of
163 ultrapure water each one. The filtrate and the cleaning fractions were combined, and total
164 Au content was determined by ICP-MS.

165 The optimization of these processes is given in the Supplementary Material
166 (Section S.4).

167

168 2.5. Concentration of AuNPs standards

169 The concentrations of the 10 nm and 30 nm AuNPs-PBS and 10 nm and 40 nm
170 AuNPs-Citrate standards were estimated by quantification of the total Au content by ICP-
171 MS. 200 μL of the AuNPs standards were digested with 1.5 mL HCl, 0.5 mL HNO_3 and
172 8 mL ultrapure water without heating. Blanks were processed in each batch of digestions.
173 Digested samples were diluted to a final volume of 20 mL with ultrapure water and
174 analyzed by ICP-MS. The ICP-MS signal intensity ratio (Au divided by Rh) was
175 expressed as concentration using an external calibration curve. The total gold
176 concentration obtained were $42,000 \pm 1,000 \text{ ng mL}^{-1}$ ($n=3$) and $27,000 \pm 1,000 \text{ ng mL}^{-1}$
177 ($n=3$) for 10 nm and 30 nm AuNPs-PBS standards, respectively; and $51,886 \pm 2,183 \text{ ng}$
178 mL^{-1} ($n=3$) and $52,186 \pm 1,327 \text{ ng mL}^{-1}$ ($n=3$) for 10 nm and 40 nm AuNPs-Citrate
179 standards, respectively.

180

181 3. Results and discussion

182

183 3.1. Optimization of the AF4-ICP-MS method

184 Several factors, such as the dimensions of the channel, the characteristics of the
185 membrane, the carrier composition and the cross flow program are critical to achieve size-
186 separation resolution in AF4 [33]. Based on previous studies, a 350 μm thick spacer and
187 regenerated cellulose membrane (MWCO of 10 kDa) were selected [34–37]. It has been
188 described that this type of membrane could improve NPs recovery because it is less
189 hydrophobic than polyethersulfone (PES), and polyvinylidenedifluoride (PVDF)
190 membranes [28].

191 Firstly, the separation of a mixture of two sizes (10 and 40 nm) of AuNPs-Citrate
192 standards without cell culture medium was attempted using the separation conditions
193 proposed by Calzolari et al. for synthesized AuNPs [34] (Supplementary material, Section
194 S.1, Table S1) using ultrapure water as carrier. Under these conditions, the separation was
195 not possible. The characteristics of the carrier composition, such as the presence of
196 surfactants, pH and ionic strength, can directly affect to the NPs stability and the
197 interaction between the NPs and the membrane [38]. Therefore, several carrier
198 compositions were studied, containing SDS at different concentrations (0.01 and 0.05 %),
199 organic compounds (methanol and sodium azide), and at different pH values
200 (Supplementary material, Section S.2). The most critical parameter was the presence of
201 SDS and its concentration. Finally, 0.01 % SDS at pH=6 was selected as carrier because
202 an adequate resolution was achieved for AuNPs standards without cell culture medium
203 (Supplementary material, Fig. S1, dash line). However, none of the previously tested
204 carrier compositions were adequate to separate different sizes of AuNPs in the presence
205 of the cell culture medium DMEM (always supplemented with 10 % FBS and antibiotics),
206 so other AF4 separation programs with 0.01 % SDS at pH 6 as carrier were tested.

207 Another critical parameter in AF4 separation is cross flow, because it produces
208 the field force controlling the distribution of particles near the membrane [39]. Different
209 cross flow programs from Bolea et al. [11] (Supplementary material, Section S.1, Table
210 S1) and some adaptations of them (Supplementary material, Section S.3 and Fig. S2) were
211 tested for a mixture of two sizes of AuNPs-Citrate and Au³⁺ ion with cell culture medium,
212 but appropriate separation conditions were not achieved. A different cross flow program
213 was proposed (Supplementary material, Section S.1, Table S1). However, the resolution
214 of two sizes of AuNPs-Citrate standards in presence of DMEM was not adequate (data
215 not shown). Then, the cross flow ramp was split in two and the slopes were modified to

216 improve resolution. The optimum conditions are shown in Table 1. As illustrated in Fig.
217 1, a mixture of 10 nm and 30 nm AuNPs-PBS standards without and with cell culture
218 medium (supplemented with 10 % FBS and antibiotics) can be separated using 0.01 %
219 SDS at pH=6 as carrier and the optimized conditions (Table 1). These separation
220 conditions were also successfully used for 10 nm and 40 nm of AuNPs-Citrate standards.

221 The membrane recovery (expressed as a percentage) was calculated as the ratio
222 between the recovered mass after analysis and the initial injected mass [40]. The analyte
223 concentration initially injected is determined in the sample without fractionation while
224 the recovered analyte is quantified in the eluting peak collected off-line after
225 fractionation. The recovery of AuNPs-PBS was satisfactory (112.25 ± 0.01 % (mean \pm
226 SD n = 3)) under these working conditions.

227 In the presence of the cell culture medium, an additional peak at 8 min (peak 1,
228 which coincides with the void peak) is observed together with a clear shift to longer
229 retention times for all the AuNPs sizes (Fig. 1). Therefore, transformations in the presence
230 of the cell culture medium are evident and the use of some complementary and
231 independent techniques is required for their study.

232

233 3.2. Study of AuNPs transformations in presence of DMEM

234

235 3.2.1. Tracking the origin of the additional peak found by AF4-ICP-MS

236 Firstly, the 10 and 30 nm AuNPs-PBS standards, individually and mixed, and
237 Au³⁺ in DMEM were analyzed by AF4-ICP-MS. Fig. 2a and Fig. 2b show the fractograms
238 of individual 10 nm (250 ng mL⁻¹) and 30 nm (500 ng mL⁻¹) AuNPs-PBS standards,
239 respectively. Peak 1 at 8 min appears in both fractograms but the intensity of the relative
240 signal is higher in the fractogram of 10 nm NPs. Figure 2c shows a fractogram of a

241 mixture of 10 nm and 30 nm AuNPs-PBS standards at 100 and 500 ng/mL, respectively,
242 and another fractogram of the same size mixture at 250 and 500 ng/mL, respectively.
243 When the concentration of 10 nm AuNPs-PBS increased, both peak 1 and the peak
244 corresponding to the 10 nm NPs increased. Fig. 2d shows the fractograms of Au³⁺ in
245 presence of cell culture medium (the standard of Au³⁺ without cell culture medium cannot
246 be determined by AF4). The retention time of Au³⁺ in this fractogram (Fig. 2d) is the
247 same as that of peak 1 in the fractograms of AuNPs (Fig. 2a, b and c).

248 However, the retention time coincidence is not sufficient evidence to set its origin.
249 It could be ionic Au³⁺ produced in an oxidation process of the AuNPs, but its presence in
250 the standards cannot be discarded by AF4-ICP-MS because free Au³⁺ cannot be seen by
251 this technique in these solutions. Therefore, we are going to use CU as complementary
252 technique to test the presence of ionic Au in the AuNPs standards. The combination of
253 centrifugation and filtration is an effective way to separate ions from NPs because of the
254 small pore sizes of the filter device. ICP-MS was used to quantify total Au concentration
255 in the filtrate.

256 The CU procedure was optimized (Supplementary material, Section S.4) and
257 applied to 10 nm and 30 nm AuNPs-PBS (500 ng mL⁻¹) and 10 nm and 40 nm AuNPs-
258 Citrate (480.43 ng mL⁻¹ and 483.20 ng mL⁻¹, respectively) standards. No trace of Au were
259 found in any of the standards tested.

260 Therefore, peak 1 observed by AF4-ICP-MS (Fig. 1, and Fig. 2 a, b, and c) could
261 be ionic Au released from the AuNPs through an oxidation processes induced by the cell
262 culture medium. This ionic Au would be associated to proteins or other components of
263 the medium leading to low-molecular Au species. Moreover, 10 nm would be more easily
264 oxidizable than 30 nm AuNPs-PBS, because the signal of peak 1 is greater for 10 nm (Fig
265 2a vs Fig. 2b). This could suggest that 10 nm AuNPs-PBS were more reactive due to their

266 small size and high surface to volume ratio. Similar oxidation processes have been
267 reported by other authors. Bolea et al. determined Ag^+ in 15 nm AgNPs standards after
268 ultrafiltration, but this content was much lower than that found after by AF4-ICP-MS,
269 therefore the oxidation of the AgNPs during the cytotoxicity assay should not be
270 disregarded [11]. An oxidation process was also described by Lopez-Sanz et al. in the
271 analysis of 10 and 30 nm AuNPs-PBS in cell culture medium (DMEM) and cells by
272 HPLC-ICP-MS [12].

273

274 3.2.2. Changes in sizes

275 An increase in retention times was observed in the fractograms of AuNPs with
276 cell culture medium (Fig. 1). These changes could be related to an increase in the
277 hydrodynamic volume of AuNPs. Firstly, the effect of the incubation time (0 and 24 h at
278 37 °C) was studied by AF4-ICP-MS (Supplementary material, Section S.5 and Fig. S3).
279 The retention times corresponding to AuNPs were slightly shifted to higher values when
280 the incubation time was longer. These results are in agreement with the characterization
281 of silver NPs in culture medium carried out by Bolea et al. [11].

282 A linear relationship between the logarithm of the retention ratio (elution time
283 corresponding to the void peak divided by the retention time for a given particle) ($\log R$)
284 and the logarithm of the diameter in nanometres ($\log d$) was proposed by Bolea et al. for
285 size characterization of AgNPs in consumer products, using AF4 separation with on-line
286 UV-vis and ICP-MS detection [41]. Following this approach, the calibration curve was
287 constructed with 10, 30, 40, 60 and 80 nm AuNPs standards ($\log R = -0.4442 \log d +$
288 0.2515 , $R^2 = 0.9871$) (Supplementary material, Section S.6, Fig. S4), and it was used to
289 estimate the AuNPs size in cell culture medium. For the 10 and 30 nm AuNPs-PBS
290 standards with cell culture medium after 0 h of incubation, the calculated particle size,

291 using the observed retention time of 16 and 25 min, respectively (Fig. S3), and the linear
292 regression equation (Fig. S4), corresponded to a modal size of 18 and 48 nm, respectively.
293 After 24 h of incubation at 37 °C, the calculated particle size corresponded to a modal
294 size of 26 (19 min) and 57 (27 min) nm for the 10 and 30 nm AuNPs-PBS standard,
295 respectively. As can be seen, both the presence of DMEM and the incubation time
296 increase the hydrodynamic volume of the AuNPs. This increase in size of AuNPs may be
297 due to the formation of protein corona and/or agglomerates/aggregates.

298 Frequently, UV-vis absorption spectrophotometry has been used to examine these
299 types of transformations because spherical AuNPs have a unique surface plasmon
300 resonance (SPR), which is clearly visible as a peak in the range between 520 and 580 nm
301 for particle diameters between 2.5 and 100 nm [42]. The UV-vis absorption spectra of
302 DMEM, 10 nm AuNPs-Citrate pure standard (51,886 ng mL⁻¹), and 10 nm AuNPs-Citrate
303 diluted with DMEM to concentrations used in *in vitro* assays (103.77 ng mL⁻¹) were
304 registered (using ultrapure water as reference) (Fig. 3). The AuNPs standard displayed a
305 SPR band at 520 nm and DMEM has an absorbance maximum at 560 nm. The spectrum
306 of AuNPs diluted with cell culture medium is similar to DMEM, but the absorbance is
307 greater. The increase in absorbance could indicate the formation of protein corona.
308 Different authors have described that when NPs increase their size, their SPR band shows
309 a bigger intensity [42]. This indicates the formation of the ground state complex between
310 proteins and NPs [44]. NPs can interact with the surrounding biomolecules in biological
311 fluids. In fact, proteins are usually adsorbed onto NPs surface forming the protein corona
312 and therefore NPs can be affected by the nature and composition of the protein [45–47].

313 To have a closer insight into this process, we studied the interaction of AuNPs and
314 BSA. The reason to choose this protein is that DMEM is commonly supplemented with
315 FBS, and BSA is one of the most represented protein in FBS. BSA (2.5 mg mL⁻¹) was

316 incubated for 24 h at 37 °C without and with different concentrations of 10 nm AuNPs-
317 Citrate (103.77, 207.54 and 518.86 ng mL⁻¹). Fig. 4 shows the absorption spectra of BSA
318 without and with AuNPs, where the absorbance signal at 280 nm increased in the presence
319 of increasing concentration of AuNPs. This result is in agreement with other studies
320 carried out with different sizes of AgNPs (2.6, 10 and 23 nm), suggesting that also AgNPs
321 could be associated with BSA [44]. Factors that could affect the association between BSA
322 and AuNPs, such as incubation time, and size and stabilizing medium of AuNPs, were
323 then studied (Supplementary material, Section S.7, Fig. S5 and Fig. S6). Among these
324 factors, the most significant was the incubation time, especially after 96 h of incubation.
325 According to literature, this suggests that BSA, present in DMEM, promotes abundant
326 and stable protein corona clustering onto the NPs metal surface [30].

327 The formation of protein corona was confirmed by previous experiments, but the
328 formation of agglomerates/aggregates cannot be discarded. When the Van der Waals
329 forces between NPs are greater than electrostatic repulsive forces produced by the NPs
330 surface in a biological medium, the formation of agglomerates (weak bonds between
331 primary particles) or aggregates (hard bonds between primary particles) can occur
332 [48,49]. Thus, Lacerda et al., in a study of the interaction of AuNPs with common human
333 blood proteins using DLS, confirmed that the effective size of the NPs firstly increases
334 due to the formation of protein-NPs complexes and later begins to aggregate [50]. Alex
335 et al. also confirmed the aggregation of CTAB-AuNPs (nanospheres and nanorods) after
336 interaction with the human serum albumin with TEM images [51]. However, Maiorano
337 et al. did not observe these aggregates for AuNPs in two types of cell culture medium. In
338 this last study, DLS spectra showed rather monodispersed peaks over time, and no
339 evidence of NPs agglomerates/aggregates was found by TEM [13]. Therefore, different

340 results are reported in literature about this aggregation/agglomeration process with
341 different types of AuNPs and experimental conditions.

342 The use of TEM is key to study the size or aggregation/agglomeration of AuNPs,
343 and it has been used as a complementary technique in the present work. Typical TEM
344 micrographs of 10 nm and 30 nm AuNPs-PBS without and with cell culture medium
345 (incubated 24 h at 37 °C) are shown in Fig. 5. In Fig. 5a, a 10 nm AuNPs-PBS standard
346 without cell culture medium is depicted, and the average size was 9.3 ± 0.6 nm (mean \pm
347 SD). This standard incubated with cell culture medium for 24 hours had average size of
348 101 ± 60.8 nm (Fig. 5c) showing high dispersion and an increase in AuNPs size. The
349 same effect was observed for the 30 nm AuNPs-PBS standard. In this case, the average
350 size was 31.2 ± 3.8 nm for the standard solution without cell culture medium (Fig. 5b)
351 and 196 ± 98.7 nm with DMEM (Fig. 5d).

352 The size of the AuNPs after 24 h of incubation with cell culture medium is greater
353 if measured by TEM than by AF4-ICP-MS, and there could be different reasons to explain
354 this difference. It should be pointed out the high size dispersion found with TEM and that
355 the largest AuNPs are outside the separation range of AF4. This last fact could also
356 explain the decrease in the intensity of the peaks in the fractograms when the AuNPs were
357 incubated with cell culture medium (Fig. 1).

358

359 **4. Conclusions**

360 A methodology based on AF4 hyphenated to ICP-MS has been proposed to study
361 AuNPs in cell culture medium DMEM (10 % FBS). Firstly, several parameters of AF4
362 were optimized to achieve the separation of different sizes of AuNPs-PBS and AuNPs-
363 Citrate with and without the cell culture medium. The fractograms obtained by AF4-ICP-
364 MS showed that DMEM induced different transformations on AuNPs. By using the CU

365 and ICP-MS as complementary technique, we could confirm an oxidation process of the
366 AuNPs in cell culture medium and the release of ionic Au, which was associated to
367 proteins or other components. The increase in AuNPs size could be due to the formation
368 of a protein corona or to aggregation/agglomeration process, which was confirmed by
369 UV-vis and TEM, respectively.

370 The identification of AuNPs and Au³⁺ transformations in the cell culture medium
371 used for *in vitro* toxicological tests should be considered for a correct interpretation of
372 toxicological results. This information is highly relevant to achieve a better understanding
373 of the mechanisms of toxicity of NPs. The development of hyphenated techniques, such
374 as the one proposed in this work, is of major interest for complex biological samples and
375 further studies should be carried out in this field.

376

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- 554

555 **Legends to figures**

556 **Figure 1.** AF4-ICP-MS fractograms of a mixture containing 10 nm (42 ng mL⁻¹) and 30
557 nm (108 ng mL⁻¹) AuNPs-PBS standards without (black line) and with (grey line) cell
558 culture medium. Carrier: 0.01 % SDS at pH = 6. Optimal cross flow program Table 1
559 (dash line).

560

561 **Figure 2.** AF4-ICP-MS fractograms in cell culture medium (DMEM, 10 % FBS) of: a)
562 10 nm AuNPs-PBS (250 ng mL⁻¹), b) 30 nm AuNPs-PBS (500 ng mL⁻¹), c) a mixture
563 containing 100 ng mL⁻¹ (black line) or 250 ng mL⁻¹ (grey line) of 10 nm and 500 ng mL⁻¹
564 ¹ (black and grey line) of 30 nm AuNPs-PBS, and d) Au³⁺ ions (50 ng mL⁻¹). Carrier: 0.01
565 % SDS at pH = 6. Optimum cross flow program Table 1.

566

567 **Figure 3.** UV-vis absorption spectra of 10 nm AuNPs-Citrate without (51,886 ng mL⁻¹,
568 dashed line) and with (103.77 ng mL⁻¹, gray line) cell culture medium. Black line
569 corresponds to cell culture medium without AuNPs.

570

571 **Figure 4.** UV-vis absorption spectra of 2.5 mg mL⁻¹ BSA (black line) incubated for 24 h
572 at 37 °C without and with different concentrations (103.77, 207.54 and 518.86 ng mL⁻¹)
573 of 10 nm AuNPs-Citrate.

574

575 **Figure 5.** Transmission electron microscopy images of AuNPs-PBS: a) 10 nm without
576 cell culture medium, b) 30 nm without cell culture medium, c) 10 nm with cell culture
577 medium (4,200 ng mL⁻¹) and d) 30 nm with cell culture medium (2,700 ng mL⁻¹),
578 incubated for 24 h at 37 °C.

579

Table 1. Optimum instrumental conditions for the AF4-ICP-MS system.

AF4			
Channel thickness (μm)	350		
Membrane type	Regenerated cellulose; cut-off, 10 kDa		
Injection loop (μL)	50		
Carrier liquid composition	0.01 % SDS (pH 6.0)		
Focus flow (mL min^{-1})	1.3		
Detector flow (mL min^{-1})	0.5		
Cross flow program	Time (min)	Regime	Cross flow (mL min^{-1})
Injection/focusing	5	Injection flow, 0.2 mL min^{-1}	1
Separation	15	Linear decay	1 to 0.5
	25	Linear decay	0.5 to 0
	2	Constant	0

ICP-MS	
RF-Power (KW)	1.4
Plasma gas flow rate (L min^{-1})	15
Carrier gas flow rate (L min^{-1})	0.98
Nebulizer flow rate (L min^{-1})	0.9
Auxiliary gas flow rate (L min^{-1})	1
Spray chamber	Scott type
Isotopes monitored	^{197}Au , ^{103}Rh
Dwell time (ms)	100

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

Highlights

- Analytical method development for the determination of AuNPs in DMEM by AF4-ICP-MS.
- An oxidation process of the AuNPs is taking place in presence of cell culture medium.
- Formation of protein corona and aggregates/agglomerates in DMEM was demonstrated.
- AuNPs transformations in cell culture medium were confirmed by complementary techniques.
- Detection of AuNPs transformations is of major interest for toxicity tests.